

Research Article

The Innovation of a Packaging for Songkok With QR Code and Augmented Reality Technology

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Abstract: *The innovation of Songkok packaging with QR code and augmented reality is a revolutionary development in the traditional packaging of Songkok. The packaging using 300gsm material with one side coated paper and only need one die cut block. This packaging also highlights the use of QR codes and augmented reality technology to enhance the customer experience by providing a digital platform for product information, and interaction. By using QR codes, customers can access product information, contact, website, social media, and other interesting details by simply scanning the code with their smartphones. The augmented reality technology offers a 3D view of the Songkok, enabling customers to interact with the product virtually, examine it closely, and visualize how it would look when worn. This innovative packaging not only offers a new way of marketing the product but also elevates the customer experience, making it more interactive and engaging. Songkok packaging can take the form of boxes, or bags, depending on the material used and the intended function of the packing. The packaging is intended to preserve the Songkok from damage during movement and storage, as well as to make it easier to transport. Packaging may also be used as a marketing technique to increase the product's visual value and differentiate it from rivals. The packaging may be intended to represent the brand's identity, using colors, logos, and other branding elements to stand out on the marketplace.*

Keywords: songkok packaging, qr code, augmented reality.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Songkok packaging serves as both commercial and storage protection. Songkok items are protected from dust by packaging. If this Songkok product is exposed to dust, it might degrade Songkok's quality and shorten its lifespan, causing Songkok damage. Because the buyer of Songkok often wears the same Songkok for as long as it is still in excellent condition, the packaging can give protection and long shelf life, making Songkok maintenance rather difficult. As a result, Songkok products have benefited from Songkok packaging. Customers will use packaging as a storage container for maintaining quality for a longer period. Additionally, with the incorporation of technological advancements like QR and augmented reality on Songkok packaging, it can give variety and appeal to customers while increasing the marketing rate.

To produce something innovative, we must think creatively and widely in order to discover ideas that will enhance our own potential for creativity. An idea regarding innovation requires three major steps: the concept, the implementation concept, and the outcomes that occur from applying the concept and have an impact on Songkok packaging. The development of digital technology in the present day is Qr and augmented reality (AR) packaging. AR is interactive and 3D-registered, combining real and virtual items. The use of QR codes and augmented reality (AR) in Songkok packaging can create a new perspective and entice consumers. Customers may view immediately the technology used in Qr and Augmented Reality (AR) with extra information by simply utilizing a smartphone. Morton Heilig pioneered augmented reality technology in 1962, defining it as a condition in which the user may view a mix of virtual things and the actual environment in real-time. Furthermore, a quick reaction code (QR) is a two-dimensional barcode (see image opposite) that can be read by a device such as a mobile device (camera phone) or laptop computer and, once accessible, allows you to execute an activity. Songkok packaging that incorporates augmented reality and QR codes is an innovation that can boost sales promotion and marketing while also attracting customer attention. This study is focused on finding the right combination of songkok packaging with Augmented Reality and QR code for marketing so that the efficacy of utilizing this material as a delivery of information and reading material may have an advantages and effective influence on users and consumers.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

Effective packaging must be created through the design process in order to function as a tool for storing and distributing information as well as protecting the product. The use of researched 300 gsm art card in this packaging for songkok products ensures that the quality of the product is maintained and the item is protected to prevent it from getting dirty or damaged during transport. When printing using an offset press, high quality prints that accurately reflect the product and brand are possible. The pre-press, press and post-press phases of the printing process must be carried out correctly to give the expected results. The packaging also acts as a novelty by turning nearby locations into centers of employment and education. This improves the overall quality of the product and customer experience. The software also makes inventory management easier, making it easier for firms to track their inventory. Overall, a methodical approach to packaging design and creation ensures that the product is protected, information is conveyed efficiently, and the customer experience is enhanced.

3. FINDINGS

Songkok packaging can take the form of boxes, pouches, or bags, depending on the material used and the intended function of the packing. The packaging is intended to preserve the Songkok from damage during movement and storage, as well as to make it easier to transport. Packaging may also be used as a marketing technique to increase the product's visual value and differentiate it from rivals. The packaging may be intended to represent the brand's identity, using colors, logos, and other branding elements to stand out on the marketplace

Figure 1. Technical drawing of songkok packaging

The development of this packaging will benefit the client and the company. The majority of Muslim men in Malaysia wear songkok for official events, celebrations, worship, and other activities. For Muslim men, it is a common accessory that they will wear again. To ensure that this product lasts longer, appropriate and suitable storage techniques are important. The consumer would surely keep the package with it to ensure the Songkok's durability. The packaging's design is also the key focus because it will leave a positive impression on both the customer and the business. Songkok packaging featuring QR and AR technologies may be utilized for branding and marketing. To make the packaging more attractive to consumers, companies might include their logo, brand colors, and other design elements. The QR code and AR technology may also be used to promote the company and its products by giving interactive and engaging experiences to customers. Songkok packaging with QR and AR may be utilized to enhance the online purchasing experience, which is becoming more popular. Customers may access product information, videos, and 3D models by scanning the QR code on the packaging, allowing them to make quicker decisions about their purchases. This technology may also be used to deliver personalized recommendations to customers based on their past web activity.

Figure 2. Augmented reality and QR code.

4. DISCUSSION

The emergence of proactive packaging significantly altered how consumers engage with products. By incorporating components like QR codes and augmented reality, brands can give their customers a more convenient and personalised buying experience. One of its most significant benefits is the proactive packaging's guarantee that the product won't be harmed. This is crucial for accessories like songkok because even minor damage might reduce the final product's quality. Customers can be guaranteed that proactive packaging will ensure that their products arrive in pristine shape. In addition, QR codes that connect to all platforms, including websites, social media, WhatsApp, and Shopee, have made it simpler for consumers to learn more about items and businesses. By just scanning the code with their smartphone, customers may browse Songkok Exclusive website and social media profiles to learn more about the benefits of the company's products, engage with other customers, and even make purchases. Because of this, customers will have a more pleasant experience, which will make it simpler for them to interact with businesses and make wise buying decisions. Next, augmented reality is one of the breakthroughs that can boost the market. By allowing customers to see behind-the-scenes, brands can increase their customers' appreciation of the product and interest in the brand. This is especially true when a variety of songkok kinds are shown in the movie in an appealing and modern fashion, which makes it simpler for customers to comprehend and relate to the product. Overall, using a logical approach while designing and creating packaging guarantees that the product is safeguarded, information is efficiently transmitted, and the consumer experience is improved.

Figure 3. songkok packaging

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the development of this packaging will benefit the client and the company. The majority of Muslim men in Malaysia wear songkok for official events, celebrations, worship, and other activities. For Muslim men, it is a common accessory that they will wear again. To ensure that this product lasts longer, appropriate and suitable storage techniques are important. The consumer would surely keep the package with it to ensure the Songkok's durability. The packaging's design is also the key focus because it will leave a positive impression on both the customer and the business. The primary goals are lowering packaging costs and replacing outdated, manually manufactured packaging. This packaging will definitely reduce the overall packaging cost. Additionally, it will be beneficial to the user because they will retain the goods in the box to prevent damage. According to my recommendation, this packaging must be developed with innovation on the packaging to boost customer interest and expand the market to the wider public.

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